

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

RM4

DELIVERABLE n. 15: CIC-39 orphan designation in DMD

SPOKE N. 5 - Industry of Health and Silver Economy

Version history

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The SOCE modulator CIC-39, a lead compound endowed with high selectivity over other Ca²⁺-permeable channels, good pharmacokinetic properties and excellent safety profile, developed through a collaborative project between University of Piemonte Orientale (UPO) and ChemiCare, has received the Orphan Drug Designation by EMA for the treatment of Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD). The Orphan Drug Designation was granted in the European Union on 13 January 2013.

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EU/3/22/2628 - orphan designation for treatment of gain-of-function mutations of STIM1 and ORAI1 related diseases

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3-(1-(2',3'-dimethoxy-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)benzoic acid

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Overview

This medicine was designated as an orphan medicine for the treatment of gain-of-function mutations of STIM1 and ORAI1 related diseases in the European Union on 21 June 2022.

This means that the developer will receive scientific and regulatory support from EMA to advance their medicine to the stage where they can apply for a [marketing authorisation](#).

[Orphan designation](#) does not mean the medicine is available or authorised for use. All medicines, including designated orphan medicines, must be authorised before they can be marketed and made available to patients in the EU.

During the medicine's development, doctors may be able to enrol patients in [clinical trials](#) investigating the medicine. For information on ongoing [clinical trials](#) in the EU, see:

- [EU Clinical Trials Register](#)
- [ClinicalTrials.gov](#)

<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/orphan-designations/eu-3-22-2628>